

SENSITIVITIES OF THERMAL ANOMALIES FROM HIGH THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY FORMATIONS IN THE WILLISTON BASIN

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Abstract

A numerical model case-study in the Williston Basin was used to investigate thermal anomalies at the top of high thermal conductivity formations. In the Williston Basin, a thick Devonian halite formation, the Prairie Evaporite, is underlain by dolomite formations, and both have high thermal conductivities. The temperature at the bottom of the production well was sensitive to site-specific ranges in thermal conductivities of 2.8 to 5.1 W m⁻¹ °C⁻¹, boundary temperatures of 98 to 154°C, and formation thicknesses of 385 to 534 m. Temperatures were calculated at 86 to 135°C at the top of the Prairie Evaporite.

1. Introduction

Heat in sedimentary basins is primarily transmitted by conduction. Minerals such as halite and dolomite have thermal conductivities 2 to 4 times higher than other sedimentary rocks (Grasby et al., 2012). The objective was to quantify the sensitivities of the magnitude of the thermal anomaly for a geothermal system targeting the Prairie Evaporite formation and underlying dolomite formations in the Williston Basin, Saskatchewan (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Location of the study area in the Williston Basin and thicknesses of targeted formations.

2. Methods and techniques

A numerical model was used to investigate heat flow in the Prairie Evaporite, depth to top 2525 m, and underlying dolomite formations (Fig. 1) using estimated ranges for thermal conductivity (Firoozy, 2016), thicknesses (TGI Williston Basin Working Group, 2008) and temperature at the top of the Red River formation (Manz, 2011). The finite element code FEFLOW (Diersch, 2014) was used to complete the heat flow analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1 Temperatures at the top of the Prairie Evaporite with varying heat flow parameters.

Thermal Cond. (W m ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹)	Boundary Temp (°C)	Thickness (m)	Prairie Temp (°C)
3.9	126	460	111
5.1	126	460	114
2.8	126	460	106
3.9	154	460	135
3.9	98	460	86
3.9	126	534	109
3.9	126	385	113

Drilling depths can be reduced in sedimentary basins by targeting high thermal conductivity formations, which result in warm temperature anomalies (Table 1). However, the temperature boundary at the top of the Red River had the greatest influence on temperature at the top of the Prairie Evaporite. Increased formation thickness resulted in decreased temperature in the Prairie Evaporite at the same Red River temperature boundary.

4. Conclusions

Modeled study area temperatures at the top of the Prairie Evaporite ranged from 86 to 135°C and were sensitive to thermal conductivity, underlying temperatures, and formation thickness.

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